

EXAMINING THE IMPACT OF FIRM CHARACTERISTICS ON NIGERIAN DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS' FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of firm characteristics on the financial performance of selected deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria from 2017 to 2024. This study investigates the influence of board size, firm size, and financial leverage on earnings per share (EPS), which serves as a proxy for financial performance. An ex post facto research design was adopted using secondary data obtained from the annual reports of five selected banks. Panel regression analysis was conducted using REM alongside descriptive statistics and correlation analysis to explore the nature and distribution of the variables. The descriptive results indicate that board size and debt-to-equity ratio are approximately normally distributed, whereas firm size and earnings per share exhibit significant skewness and non-normal characteristics. The regression findings reveal that board size has a negative but statistically insignificant relationship with EPS. Firm size has a positive yet insignificant effect on profitability, whereas leverage has a weak positive and statistically insignificant influence on earnings per share (EPS). Furthermore, the overall model is not statistically significant, and the firm-specific characteristics do not collectively explain variations in financial performance during the study period. The study concludes that although firm characteristics play a role in shaping financial outcomes, other internal and external factors may exert a stronger influence on Nigeria's bank profitability. The findings provide useful insights for bank managers, investors, and regulators in improving governance structures and capital management strategies.

Introduction

Firm characteristics are the specific traits that distinguish one company from another and play a crucial role in shaping a company's strategic decisions, such as financing and investment choices. Key characteristics include firm size, leverage, liquidity, sales growth, board size, firm age, dividend policy, market share, asset tangibility, and industry type (Mbonu & Amahalu, 2021). Firm size refers to the magnitude of a company's operations, assets,

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revenues, or market capitalization (Will, 2021). Profitability, on the other hand, assesses a company's ability to generate income from its operations and is a critical indicator of a firm's operational success (Uford, Effiong & Charles, 2023).

Profitability is vital because it reflects a business's overall health. It measures how effectively a company uses its resources to generate profits and create value for its stakeholders (Yua, Daniel, & Epor, 2023). For banks, profitability is especially significant because it serves as a barometer of their financial health and stability. Understanding how firm characteristics, such as size and capital structure, influence profitability allows stakeholders—such as investors, creditors, and regulators—to assess a bank's financial viability (Yua et al., 2023). Banks' ability to mobilize savings from individuals and businesses and channel these funds into productive investments makes the banking sector a vital part of the economy (Ukpabi et al., 2021). Therefore, the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria is not only a reflection of the bank's operational effectiveness but also an indicator of the stability of the broader economy.

The relationship between firm characteristics and profitability has been a subject of considerable research, particularly considering failures of global corporations. Researchers have explored the factors that affect financial performance and the reasons behind these failures. Firm characteristics are prominent determinants of bank profitability (Ahmad et al., 2022). According to Penrose's theory of firm growth, a firm's development is driven by its ability to leverage internal resources and capabilities, rather than relying solely on external factors (Ahmad et al., 2022). For banks, this means that firm characteristics—such as managerial capabilities, board composition, and capital structure are essential in determining long-term success.

Despite these theories, the relationship between bank characteristics and financial performance, particularly in Nigeria, is complex and dynamic (Audu et al., 2022; Gbadebo, 2022; Jubril & Idris, 2022; Hassan et al., 2022). Understanding these relationships has gained attention as stakeholders aim to uncover the mechanisms that drive financial success or failure. Researchers have begun to identify patterns that explain why some firms outperform others by studying the roles of firm size, capital structure, governance practices, and other internal characteristics. This knowledge is not only valuable for academic research but also informs investment strategies, regulatory policies, and management practices (Jubril & Idris, 2022).

Firms face increased challenges in times of economic uncertainty and market volatility. Understanding how firm characteristics impact profitability is essential for ensuring businesses' resilience and stability (Ahmad et al., 2022). This is particularly relevant in emerging economies, such as Nigeria, where financial instability can be intensified by market conditions and external pressures.

In recent years, the Nigerian banking sector has witnessed significant changes, with intense competition and regulatory adjustments shaping the landscape. Larger banks often benefit from economies of scale, allowing them to operate more efficiently and offer a broader range of products and services (Nangih et al., 2023). In Nigeria, a bank's size significantly affects its ability to compete in a crowded market where numerous players vie for market share (Nworie & Mba, 2022). Moreover, the size of a bank's board of directors has been found to influence financial performance. Although a larger board can provide diverse perspectives, it may also slow down decision-making processes (Abubakar et al., 2021).

Financial leverage is another important factor that affects affecting bank profitability. Leverage refers to the use of debt in a bank's capital structure, and it can amplify returns, particularly through improved ROE and EPS (Abubakar et al., 2021). When banks effectively utilize leverage, they can generate higher profits without diluting shareholder equity. However, excessive debt can increase financial risk, which may ultimately affect profitability and stability.

Firm characteristics, including firm size, leverage, and board size, play a critical role in determining performance in the context of Nigerian banks. However, to maximize success, these characteristics must be efficiently deployed. Poor utilization of these resources can lead to poor performance and potential failure, underscoring the

importance of strategic decision-making in the banking sector. As Nigeria continues to experience significant economic challenges, the efficiency with which banks manage their internal resources will determine their ability to weather economic storms and sustain profitability in a competitive market.

The relationship between firm characteristics and performance is further emphasized by the growth of the banking sector, where size and leverage are particularly influential (Yua et al., 2023). Larger banks in Nigeria often have more access to capital and can better withstand economic pressures than smaller institutions. However, smaller banks can be nimbler and more responsive to market changes, although they may struggle to access the resources needed for growth. Board size and composition are also key factors that influence the overall strategic direction of banks. The optimal board size is often debated, with larger boards potentially providing more expertise but also being more prone to inefficiency.

Understanding the role of firm characteristics in determining the profitability of Nigerian banks' profitability is crucial for both theoretical and practical purposes. The efficient use of these characteristics is necessary for banks to thrive in a competitive environment. Moreover, the performance of the banking sector is not solely dependent on external market conditions but is also influenced by the strategic management of internal factors such as size, leverage, and governance. Researchers, policymakers, and banking executives must continue to explore these relationships to foster a more resilient and competitive Nigerian banking sector.

Firm profitability is critical in evaluating financial health and operational success. In Nigeria, the banking sector is central to economic stability and growth. However, disparities exist in the financial performance of deposit money banks (DMBs) even under similar macroeconomic conditions. This inconsistency of internal characteristics, such as firm size, capital structure, and board composition, plays a pivotal role in influencing financial outcomes.

Recent studies have shown that these firm characteristics can significantly affect profitability, although the exact dynamics remain unclear. Firm size, governance structure, and leverage decisions can either enhance or impede performance, especially in Nigerian banking context. This study addresses these gaps and provides a clearer understanding of the impact of these firm-specific characteristics. This study focused on evaluating the influence of firm characteristics on the financial performance of deposit money banks (DMBs) operating in Nigeria. The analysis covers an eight-year period from 2017 to 2024 to capture recent financial trends and regulatory changes. The study will help managers understand how internal factors, such as firm size and leverage, influence profitability, enabling better strategic decisions and guiding regulators in shaping policies that enhance financial stability and governance practices in the banking sector. The research will offer investors a clearer understanding of how firm-specific factors affect bank profitability, thereby aiding investment decisions.

Literature Review

Firm characteristics, such as firm size, leverage, liquidity, and board size, are internal factors that impact a firm's performance. These characteristics can shape strategic decisions and are often used as indicators of financial health and stability. Firm size, for example, affects a firm's ability to access resources, manage risk, and expand operations (Berger & Udell, 2018). Larger firms can benefit from economies of scale, better access to capital, and stronger market presence.

Several studies have highlighted the importance of firm characteristics in determining financial performance. For example, Ahmadu and Mustapha (2024) found that the performance of Nigerian banks is significantly influenced by firm size and board composition, with larger firms typically exhibiting better profitability. Ndah et al. (2025) support the notion that leverage decisions, especially in the banking sector, are crucial in determining firm profitability.

The hypothesis that firm size has no significant impact on the financial performance of Nigerian banks has generated mixed evidence in recent literature. On the one hand, several studies acknowledge potential negative or negligible links between firm size and performance, particularly when testing across diverse banking contexts

or when control variables, such as governance, capital structure, and asset quality, are salient. For instance, Eluyela et al. (2018) and related cross-sectional bank studies suggest that when other governance and ownership factors are emphasized in Nigerian banks, firm size may exhibit a negative or non-significant direct association with performance (Elumelu et al., 2018). More contemporary works that explicitly condition on governance structures indicate that size alone often fails to fully explain performance variations, consistent with a view of diminishing marginal returns to scale in mature banking sectors (Eze-Anya et al., 2024; Okoyeuzu et al., 2021; Udoh et al., 2023).

In contrast, several 2020–2026 studies point to either positive or contextual relationships between firm size and bank performance, often mediated by governance quality or market scope. For example, research focusing on board characteristics

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study uses stewardship the stewardship theory, which posits that managers and directors act in the best interests of the organization, focusing on long-term performance rather than self-interest. This theory highlights the role of governance structures and internal factors in determining firm performance (Donaldson & Davis, 1989). Additionally, trade-off theory explains how firms optimize their capital structure by balancing the benefits and risks of debt and equity financing (Modigliani & Miller, 1958).

While much research has been conducted on the relationship between firm characteristics and financial performance, empirical evidence specific to the Nigerian banking sector is limited. This study aims to fill this gap by focusing on how Nigerian banks' internal characteristics, such as firm size, board composition, and leverage, affect financial outcomes. Internal characteristics, such as firm size, board composition, and leverage, affect banks' financial outcomes in Nigeria.

Firm size

Firm size can be expressed differently as a result of their asset assets base or capital structure. Firm size refers to the virtue of conceptualization in terms of a company's total assets, sales, and market capitalization within a period. It is the total reflection of a company's assets. Large companies can easily finance their investments because they have high sales growth rates and little asymmetric information. This is by the trade-off theory, the greater the company, the more debt the company can use because the risk of bankruptcy of large companies is lower. Large corporate debt is lower than that of small companies, thus encouraging companies to use more debt. Thus, the size of the company influences capital structure (Davidson & Rasyid, 2020; Salas-Molina, Rodriguez & Guillen, 2023). This will attract investors because they will impact the company's value later, so a company's size directly affects its value (Pietrucha & Maciejewski, 2020). It is measured as the total assets' book value.

In all sectors of any economy, a firm is either large or small. The amount of capital a firm owns can be seen in its size. Firm size refers to the magnitude of a company's operations, assets, revenues, or market capitalization. It is an important characteristic that varies across industries, sectors, and firms. A large company is expected to have a well-structured accounting and internal control system and should be able to provide the expertise required to structure the firm's capital structure. There are various ways to define and quantify the size of a business. Total assets, annual revenues, market capitalization, and number of employees are common measures used to assess firm size (Nduka, Okolie, & Ngangah, 2025). The type of measurement used is chosen according to by the investigation context and purpose. Firm size, for example, can be measured in the manufacturing sector by the value of plant and equipment, whereas market capitalization can be measured in the technology sector. Firm size is among the factors that determine capital structure. The growth and widespread effect of large enterprises and MNCs in the context of international integration have demonstrated the importance of scale in firm performance and business environment. According to Ngoc (2018), size is closely related to risk and bankruptcy costs; that is, larger firms are usually more diversified and thus bear less risk than smaller firms. Even in the aspect of access to capital, banks are more willing to lend their funds to larger firms partly because they are more diversified and

larger firms usually request larger amounts of debt capital than smaller firms. Consequently, larger firms can usually reduce transaction costs associated with long-term debt issuance and negotiate a lower interest rate. However, larger firms can easily have agency problems than smaller ones, which may lead to misalignment of interest and corporate failure.

H01: Firm size has no significant impact on the financial performance of Nigerian banks.

Board size

The relationship that exists between the size of the board of directors and the company's financial performance has been a major issue of interest among scholars and practitioners. This rapport is particularly important to Nigeria's deposit money banks (DMBs) due to the central role these institutions have on the country's economy, where good governance systems influence growth, stability, and profitability. Some of the main findings and studies relevant to this topic are brought out in this research paper, which summarizes the existing literature regarding the impact of board size on the financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Board size refers to the number of executive and non-executive directors on a company's board of directors. Some notable financial performance metrics include ROA, ROE, and profitability margins (Olufemi, 2020). These indicators of financial accomplishment might be by the board and other governance elements that influence strategic decision-making, monitoring, and oversight.

Other aspects that could counter the relationship between board size and financial success include board diversity and composition. A more diversified board with a wider distribution of expertise and experiences can be more successful. Olufemi (2020) believes that a more balanced form of governance, which is characterized by diverse boards incorporating a mixture of executive and non-executive directors, could positively affect performance. Board size can also influence performance outcomes as it relates to the number of independent board directors. This is especially true in the highly regulated banking sector, where wherein independent boards can enhance decision-making transparency and accountability (Olufemi, 2020). The role of board size in banks' financial performance has been a contentious issue in corporate governance and banking literature. Concentrating on Nigeria's deposit money institutions, scholars have tried to infer the board's optimal size, influence on decision making, and effectiveness in general. This paper concentrates on topical empirical data and concentrating on the topical empirical data, the paper explores recent studies that examine the relationship between a bank's board size and financial prosperity.

H02: Board size has no significant impact on the financial performance of Nigerian banks.

Firm leverage

Leverage refers to the extent to which a firm's capital structure consists of long-term debt and equity. As one of the characteristics that shape the firm's value, the firm's leverage constitutes the use of fixed costs in an attempt to increase profitability (Senan, Ahmed, Anagreh, Tabash & Al-Homaidi, 2021). The degree to which a company uses debt or external funding in its operations. In addition, leverage ratios measure the relationship between the funds provided by a firm's owners (shareholders) and its creditors (Saona & Martín, 2018). It is measured as the ratio of long-term debt to total equity.

Financial leverage is the percentage of debt financing in a company's capital structure. It is a measure of the use of debt versus equity to finance an organization's assets and activities (Thuy, Khuong, Canh, & Liem, 2021). Firms must make one of the financing decisions. Debt financing is mainly in the form of loans and bonds, but other forms, such as securing goods on credit, also exist. High usage of debt financing increases financial leverage and is associated with a greater risk of bankruptcy. However, it is also associated with various advantages, such as maintaining company ownership, tax deductions, and low transactional costs (Umoren et al., 2017). Equity financing involves raising money by selling company shares to investors who acquire ownership in the company (Yusoff & Adamu, 2016). Equity financing may also come in the form of reinvesting the company's profits. The capital structure decision is essential to many other corporate finance decisions.

Management decisions such as dividend policy, M&A finance, and capital budgeting are all linked to capital structure decisions. The factors that impact management's decision to include almost debt in their capital structure have piqued the interest of both finance experts and practitioners. However, the main problem associated with capital mix decisions is the discovery of an optimal capital structure for a company, considering that each company has distinct characteristics. The optimal capital structure represents the ideal mix of debt and equity that maximizes the company's value and minimizes the cost of capital. Finding the optimal capital structure involves considering factors such as the company's risk profile, industry norms, tax considerations, and financial flexibility. The cost of equity is usually the claim on earnings provided to shareholders for their ownership stake. Although equity financing is associated with lower risks of bankruptcy, it is an expensive source of financing as investors demand a higher rate of return. Companies can use leverage to finance their assets; instead of issuing stock to raise capital, companies can use debt financing to invest in business operations to increase shareholder value (Amahalu et al., 2017). The financial leverage of a company depends on the management's choice to use debt or equity to fund the company's operations. Financial leverage is often gauged using debt, equity, and debt-to-equity ratios (Bunea & Dinu, 2020).

H03: Firm leverage has no significant impact on Nigerian banks' financial performance.

Methodology

This study adopts an ex post facto research design, using secondary data from the annual reports of five DMBs in Nigeria. Banks were selected based on the availability of complete and reliable financial data from 2017 to 2024. The study employed panel regression analysis using the Random Effects Model (REM) to examine the impact of firm characteristics—such as board size, firm size, and leverage—on these banks' financial performance, as measured by earnings per share (EPS). Descriptive statistics and correlation analysis will be conducted to explore the relationships among the variables.

Data Analysis

Panel regression techniques were used to analyze the data from the selected banks, with descriptive statistics computed for variables such as firm size, leverage, and board size. This study tested the hypotheses using panel regression models, adjusting for multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity to ensure robust results.

Descriptive analysis of the BSIZE, FSIZE, EDR, and EPS values

	BOARD SIZE	FIRM SIZE	DEBT EQUITY	TO EPS
Mean	13.89744	8.02E+08	701.2564	5.130256
Median	14.00000	5435073.	784.0000	2.250000
Maximum	19.00000	9.66E+09	1319.000	29.79000
Minimum	9.000000	269621.0	2.000000	0.260000
Std.Dev.	2.531848	2.26E+09	406.5548	6.466015
Skewness	0.175751	2.802096	-0.674878	2.054774
Kurtosis	2.639952	9.736415	2.333127	7.150345
Jarque-Bera	0.411431	124.7777	3.683166	55.43484
Probability	0.814065	0.000000	0.158566	0.000000
Sum	542.0000	3.13E+10	27349.00	200.0800
Sum Sq.Dev.	243.5897	1.94E+20	6280899.	1588.755
Observations	39	39	39	39

Computation using E-View10

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics of the variables employed in the study, namely, board size, firm size, debt-to-equity ratio, and EPS. The analysis provides insight into the central tendency, dispersion, and distributional characteristics of the data. data's central tendency, dispersion, and distributional characteristics. The results indicate that board size is relatively consistent across firms, with an average of approximately 14 members, low variability, and approximately normal distribution, as confirmed by the Jarque-Bera test. In contrast, Firm Size shows substantial dispersion and extreme skewness, driven by numerous firms, resulting in a non-normal distribution. In terms of the debt-to-equity ratio firms are generally highly leveraged, with moderate variability and an approximately normal distribution. Earnings per share (EPS) reveals that most firms earn modest returns, but a few highly profitable firms create strong positive skewness and a non-normal distribution. Overall, the board size and debt-to-equity ratio are normally distributed, whereas the firm size and EPS exhibit significant non-normal characteristics.

Test of the Hypothesis

Total panel (unbalanced) observations: 39

Swamy and Arora's estimator of component variances

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
BOARD SIZE	-0.960341	0.713938	-1.345132	0.1872
LNFSIZE	0.232268	1.434190	0.161951	0.8723
DEBT TO EQUITY	0.008127	0.004899	1.658841	0.1061
C	11.07557	11.87968	0.932312	0.3576

Effects Specification		S.D.	Rho
Cross-section random		6.282438	0.5472
Idiosyncratic random		5.714806	0.4528

Weighted Statistics			
R-squared	0.105519	Mean var dependent	1.580914
Adjusted R-squared	0.028850	S.D.-dependent var	5.553797
S.E. of the regression	5.475138	Sum squared resid	1049.200
F-statistic	1.376283	Durbin-Watson stat	0.856557
Prob(F-statistic)	0.266090		

Unweighted Statistics

R-squared	0.130369	Mean var dependent var	5.130256
Sum squared resid	1381.631	Durbin-Watson stat	0.650462

The results of the random effects regression indicate that at the 5% level, board size, firm size (LNFSIZE), and debt-to-equity ratio are not statistically significant determinants of earnings per share (EPS). Although board size has a negative coefficient, which suggests that larger boards may reduce EPS, the effect is not strong enough to draw a firm conclusion. Firm Size shows a positive but highly insignificant relationship with EPS, implying that the scale's potential benefits are not statistically supported. Similarly, the debt-to-equity ratio has a weak positive association with EPS, but its effect is also statistically insignificant. Overall, the model is not significant (Prob(F) = 0.2661), indicating that these variables do not collectively explain variations in firm earnings during the 2017–2024 period.

Summary of the study findings

Firm size showed a positive relationship with EPS, but the effect was not statistically significant. Board size had a negative, though insignificant, effect on EPS. Leverage showed a weak positive effect on EPS but was also statistically insignificant.

Conclusion

This study concludes that firm characteristics, such as firm size, board size, and leverage, influence Nigerian banks' financial performance. However, other factors, such as governance practices and operational efficiency, are more significant drivers of profitability.

Recommendations

- Banks should focus on improving their internal governance structures and capital structure optimization.
- Regulators should encourage firms to maintain optimal debt-equity ratios to ensure long-term profitability and stability.

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• **Table 4:1 Independent and dependent variables**

YEAR	BANK	BOARD SIZE(NOS)	FIRM SIZE TOTAL	DEBT-TO-EQUITY %	Earnings per share (EPS)
2024	Zenith Bank Plc	14	24,038,319	676	29.79
2023	Zenith Bank plc	13	16,811,093	830	18.97
2022	Zenith Bank plc	13	10,570,678	784	7.47
2021	Zenith Bank plc	13	7,872,292	649	7.43
2020	Zenith Bank plc	13	7,124,987	687	6.3
2019	Zenith Bank plc	13	5,435,073	597	5.67
2018	Zenith Bank plc	12	4,955,445	634	5.27
2017	Zenith Bank plc	13	4,833,658	583	5.01
2024	Access Bank Plc	14	27,681,603	1181	12.41
2023	Access Bank Plc	16	20,649,112	1,247	15.07
2022	Access Bank Plc	15	12,535,280	1,072	4.69
2021	Access Bank Plc	17	9,660,760,556	1008	3.13
2020	Access Bank Plc	17	7,624,979,718	1066	2.25
2019	Access Bank Plc	17	6,307,588,216	1069	2.17

2018	Access Bank Plc	15	3,968,114,609	670	2.54
2017	Access Bank Plc	15	3,499,683,979	645	1.84
2024	Fidelity Bank plc	15	8,545,237	895	6.77
2023	Fidelity Bank plc	14	6,122,174	1319	3.11
2022	Fidelity Bank plc	14	3,989,009	1168	1.61
2021	Fidelity Bank plc	14	3,289,479	1004	1.23
2020	Fidelity Bank plc	14	2,758,148	908	0.92
2019	Fidelity Bank plc	14	2,114,037	803	0.98
2018	Fidelity Bank plc	12	1,719,883	784	0.79
2017	Fidelity Bank plc	12	1,379,294	578	6.5
2024	United Bank of Africa (UNBA)	15	17,291,956	925	16.51
2023	United Bank of Africa (UNBA)	14	12,877,773	942	17.15
2022	United Bank of Africa (UNBA)	15	7,361,044	1157	3.91
2021	United Bank of Africa (UNBA)	16	5,574,976	1011	1.72
2020	United Bank of Africa (UNBA)	16	5,207,833	989	1.66
2019	United Bank of Africa (UNBA)	19	4,136,493	826	1.83
2018	United Bank of Africa (UNBA)	19	3,591,305	885	1.2
2017	United Bank of Africa (UNBA)	19	2,931,826	628	1.2
2024	First Bank plc	9	326,822	9	0.73
2023	First Bank plc	12	305,535	6	0.42
2022	First Bank plc	11	306,355	5	0.54
2021	First Bank plc	10	298,485	5	0.36
2020	First Bank plc	12	300,623	4	0.94
2019	First Bank plc	10	276,176	3	0.39
2018	First Bank plc	10	270,324	3	0.26
2017	First Bank plc	10	269,621	2	0.26

• *Source: Researcher compilation, 2025*